

Deliverable 6.1

Extended and Updated project web pages and associated media channels

Project acronym:	SCIROC
Project number:	780086
Project title	European Robotics League plus Smart Cities Robot Competitions
WP number and title:	WP6 – Dissemination
WP leader:	Erik Stengler – University of the West of England (UWE) Marta Palau Franco – University of the West of England (UWE)

Organisation responsible for deliverable:	Beneficiary 1 - University of the West of England (UWE Bristol)
Deliverable author(s):	Erik Stengler – University of the West of England (UWE) Marta Palau Franco – University of the West of England (UWE)
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Dissemination Type	Website, patents filling, etc.
Dissemination level:	Public

Change log			
Version	Date	Author	Reason for change
0.1	9/03/2018	Erik Stengler	Website content + Instagram
0.2	9/03/2018	Marta Palau Franco	Tournaments + News
0.3	12/03/2018	Marta Palau Franco	Website content + social media
0.4	28/03/2018	Marta Palau Franco	Update social media descriptions.

Release approval			
Version	Date	Name and organisation	Role
1.0	29/03/2018	Matthew Studley- UWE Bristol	Project Coordinator

Summary

- **ERL website**

The type of dissemination of the WP6 deliverable D6.1 “Extended and Updated project web pages and associated media channels” is a public website and social media channels.

The European Robotics League (ERL) website was updated with new content on the about, including a new page on the SciRoc Horizon 2020 project. News, new tournaments (including the external local organisers websites) and a page on the ERL Smart City competition were added to the existing ERL website. An external page on the specific ERL Smart City tournament in Milton Keynes in 2019 will be created by the Open University and be on-line in May-June 2018. This will help to better disseminate the event and give more visibility to the ERL and ERL social channels.

The sponsor page will be updated as soon as current sponsors confirm the sponsorship for this new season starting April 2018.

The ERL website url: <http://www.robotics-league.eu>

- **ERL Social Media**

The already existing social media channels of the European Robotics League have been updated and published new information on the events, such as the workshops and awards ceremony at ERF 2018 in Tampere, Finland.

Twitter

<https://twitter.com/erlrobotleague>

Facebook

<https://es-la.facebook.com/ERLrobotleague/>

The **LinkedIn** channel used in previous years was euRobotics one. After evaluating the use of LinkedIn as a social media channel for ERL, we have decided not to have it until a foundation is created. Instead, we have created an Instagram channel, which is very popular nowadays, where we can share pictures and short video stories of the tournaments and events.

Instagram

<https://www.instagram.com/erlrobotleague/>

YouTube

The YouTube channel used in previous years was euRobotics one. We have created a YouTube channel for ERL, but it will be online when we publish the general video of the ERL in the smart city competition. This is to not to confuse the general public and participants as some of the leagues are taking new paths into urban environments. The gmail account is associated to the email address: europeanroboticsleague@gmail.com